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Muon $g-2$ Experiment and the Standard Model

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Abstract

The anomalous magnetic moment of muon, a_μ , has been used as an indication of physics beyond the Standard Model. Fermilab Muon $g-2$ experiment has published the most precise measurement of a_μ with an uncertainty of 460 parts-per-billion which shows 3.3 sigma discrepancy between the experiment and the 2020 $g-2$ Theory Initiative Standard Model prediction. We will show the recent results from the Fermilab Muon $g-2$ experiment while also briefly cover the status of the Standard Model prediction on calculating the anomalous magnetic moment of muon and discuss how the discrepancy will change with the recent updates.

1 Introduction

Using muons to probe new physics has been a very valuable tool for years, especially after BNL Muon g-2 experiment found a 3σ discrepancy between standard model calculation of the magnetic moment of muon and what was actually measured [1]. This result motivated repeating the experiment with higher precision at Fermilab.

Magnetic dipole moment of a charged particle can be expressed as

$$\vec{\mu} = g_{\mu} \frac{e}{2m} \vec{s} \quad (1)$$

where g_{μ} is the proportionality constant between spin (\vec{s}) and magnetic moment ($\vec{\mu}$) of muon, e is the elementary charge and m is mass. Dirac equation mentions that g is exactly 2 for spin-half particles such as electron or muon. However, it is known that all of the quantum effects will make the calculation more complicated when QED, hadronic and electroweak interactions are also taken into account. Hence, a new definition is created to explain how g differs from 2 as follows

$$a_{\mu} \equiv \frac{g_{\mu} - 2}{2} \quad (2)$$

where a_{μ} is the anomalous magnetic moment of muon. Measuring this anomaly could tell us if there are new particles or even forces that could possibly contribute to the anomaly. While Fermilab is hosting the effort on measuring this quantity, there is a Theory Initiative group, formed by many theoretical and experimental physicists who are trying to calculate the same effect by using what Standard Model offers.

2 Muon g-2 Experiment

2.1 Experiment Concept

Fermilab Muon g-2 experiment was designed to measure the anomalous magnetic moment of muon following the BNL concept, only with higher precision. Superconducting storage ring magnet was refurbished to accomplish 1.45 T magnetic field with 2.5 times improvement on the intrinsic uniformity. Twenty-four calorimeters composed of an array of PbF_2 crystals were used to detect the decay positrons. Two straw tracker stations, each consists of eight tracking modules with thirty-two straws, were built to make detailed measurements of the muon beam profile. Additionally, hundreds of Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) probes were installed to make a precise measurement of the the magnetic field inside the storage ring.

Fermilab Muon g-2 experiment is based on a few important concepts to achieve the targeted precision of 140 ppb. Beam is delivered to the storage ring by the Fermilab Muon Campus at 3.1 GeV/c momentum to minimize the electric field systematic caused by the Electrostatic Quadrupoles (ESQ). ESQs are designed to vertically focus the beam. Along with the kicker magnets that direct the injected muons onto central orbit, ESQs represent key roles to store the beam inside the storage ring. Storing the muons gives the opportunity to measure the time and energy of the decayed positrons and eventually calculate the anomalous spin precession frequency, ω_a , the difference between muon spin precession frequency and the cyclotron frequency. Measuring the anomaly also requires measuring the field precisely. For that, Fermilab Muon g-2 experiment uses NMR probes and map the magnetic field with high resolution. Finally, anomalous magnetic moment of muon can be obtained by using the following formula;

$$a_{\mu} = \frac{g_e \omega_a m_{\mu} \mu_p}{2 \tilde{\omega}_p m_e \mu_e} \quad (3)$$

Figure 1: Experimental values of a_μ from BNL E821 and Fermilab Run-1 along with the combined average. Purple band shows the experiment average uncertainty. Green point marks the 2020 Theory Initiative result with the green band showing the uncertainty.

where $\tilde{\omega}_p$ is the Larmor precession frequency of the proton convoluted by the beam distribution [2], ω_a is the muon spin precession frequency [3, 4] while other quantities are the fundamental constants that are gathered from other established measurements [5, 6, 7].

Fermilab's first result was published in April 2021 with 460 ppb uncertainty [8]. While this result showed an agreement with previous BNL result, it also increased the discrepancy between standard model prediction and the experiment average to 4.2σ as shown in Fig. 1.

2.2 Improvements on the Experiment

In order to achieve the systematic goal, many improvements have been implemented to the experiment after the first year of physics running. Additional to the hardware upgrades, analysis techniques and simulation studies were also improved, resulting in a reduced uncertainty on the experimental measurement.

The kicker magnet has an improved kick during the Run-3 physics running which reduced the coherent betatron oscillation (CBO) of the muons in the storage ring. Additional to the better kick, a new sub-system called Quad-RF, was implemented to the ESQs [9]. Run-5 and Run-6 data will have even more reduced CBO amplitude and muon loss rate with this addition to the experiment.

Reconstruction method was upgraded in a way that number of unresolved pileup events at the calorimeters can be reduced greatly. New algorithm was intended to improve the pileup related systematic uncertainty at least 5 times comparing to Run-1 values. Another improvement was on the second largest systematic called the phase acceptance and it was greatly reduced in Run-2/3. Phase acceptance systematic was amplified by the damaged ESQ resistors during Run-1 since the unstable voltage caused a slow change to the muon distribution during the measuring period [10].

Furthermore, measurement techniques which are used to measure the field perturbations were greatly improved in Run-2/3 and it is expected to see at least a factor of 4 reduction on the related systematic calculations.

As a result of those upgrades which provided better running conditions and improvements on the field measurement techniques, it is highly anticipated to have a factor of two reduction

on the experiment's systematic error during Run-2/3 analysis and beyond.

3 Standard Model Calculation

Theory Initiative group was founded to determine the Standard Model value of anomalous magnetic moment of muon by combining many existing calculations into one single theoretical value that will eventually be compared to the experimental value of a_μ .

Anomalous magnetic moment of muon receives contribution from quantum electrodynamics(QED), weak interactions (EW) and hadronic contributions. Hadronic contributions combine two calculations that are coming from hadronic vacuum polarization (HVP) and hadronic light by light (HLbL) contribution. While QED and EW contributions are very well understood with small uncertainties, hadronic contribution error dominates the total error on a_μ with 0.34 ppm on HVP and 0.15ppm on HLbL. With all four of them included, the total error is reported to be 0.37 ppm on the December 2020 White Paper (WP20) of the Theory Initiative group [11].

Hadronic calculations are performed by using both data-driven methods and lattice QCD. While HLbL precision demand is less than HVP, it still needs to be reduced to 10%. HVP uncertainty definitely needs to be less than 0.5% to be able to keep up with the experiment uncertainties. Fig. 2 shows a variety of HVP calculation methods and their corresponding a_μ values. While WP20 compiles two of the data-based dispersive methods as the final number, there are many lattice calculations with a total uncertainty of 2.6% which weren't included in the final number. BMW20 is the first lattice QCD calculation that reached to sub-percent error level. It seems to reduce the tension with the experiment average but it also shows tension with other data-based dispersive methods. Hence, same level of uncertainty needs to be reached by other lattice QCD groups and eventually converge on one consensus value.

Among the experiments that provide input for the calculations, there has been a new result from CMD3 collaboration that measures $e^+e^- \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-$ cross section for the HVP contribution [13]. While it was in tension with previous similar measurements, it also reduced the tension with experimental measurement of a_μ . Even though the measurement shows no obvious problem, new results from BaBar, KLOE, SND, BesIII and Belle II will help us understand this latest puzzle.

4 Outlook

First result from Fermilab Muon g-2 collaboration increased the discrepancy between standard model and the experiment average to 4.2σ . Collaboration stopped data taking in late summer of 2023 as it hit the TDR statistical uncertainty target shortly before that. With all the improvements on the hardware, measurement techniques and the analysis methods; we plan to reach 140 ppb experiment goal with the analysis of the last batch of data in 2025. Towards the end of 2020s, another Muon g-2 experiment is planned to start data-taking at J-PARC in Japan[14]. It presents a new different approach on measuring the anomaly and promises ultra-precise measurements.

Since the Standard Model prediction of a_μ is limited by the refinement of the hadronic contributions, huge amount of effort has been focusing on these contributions by the Theory Initiative group. Lattice Gauge Theory Community is working around the clock to finalize their calculations which heavily depends on the techniques and computational resources that are available. Additionally, the group is working on trying to understand the difference between Lattice QCD and data-driven methods. Eventually, they aim to reduce the HVP contribution uncertainty to 0.5% and HLbL contribution uncertainty to 10% by 2025 [15]. Hence, 2025 is going to be the showdown year to resolve many puzzles and finally get a better understanding of the discrepancy between experiment and the standard model.

Figure 2: a_μ values for the corresponding HVP calculation methods [12]. WP20 represents the 2020 Theory Initiative result which is the average of DHMZ19 and KNT19 data-driven determinations (with grey band that shows the uncertainty of WP20 result). Blue points represent several lattice QCD calculations where the blue band shows their average. While yellow band shows the uncertainty of BNL+FNAL result, grey band in the middle is the final Fermilab uncertainty goal.

5 Post-Talk Update

Fermilab Muon $g-2$ experiment published the Run-2/3 result a few weeks after this talk was given. Fig. 3 summarises all experiment results so far where the new result is compatible with the previous one with more than twice improvement on both statistical (201 ppb) and the systematic (70 ppb) uncertainty. With the world average going down to 190 ppb uncertainty, it is now more important for Theory Initiative to refine their numbers to the compatible uncertainty.

Similarly, Theory Initiative group also published a statement on the standard model prediction. A new analysis on $\pi^+\pi^-$ cross section by BABAR is underway to show an independent analysis that will eventually be a complementary work to the previous methods with reduced uncertainty. KLOE and BESIII experiments are also expecting to analyze new data which will similarly help on the scrutinizing the hadronic contributions. Given that a huge amount of efforts going on with the lattice QCD calculations, it is expected to see new lattice QCD results on the HVP contribution on sub-percent uncertainty level in near future [16].

Figure 3: Experimental values of a_μ from Fermilab Run-1, Run-2/3, Run-1+Run2/3 and BNL E821 along with the new experimental average.

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